

Gender Sensitivity among the Faculty and Employees of ASIST

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this research is to advocate gender awareness and sensitivity in the school. Specifically, it sought to measure the level of gender sensitivity among the employees of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology. The descriptive method of investigation was used to describe the teachers' and non-teaching personnel's level of gender sensitivity. The researchers sought permission from the head of the institution to conduct the proposed study, meet the respondents and distribute the checklist and questionnaires to them. Responses were retrieved, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted. In conclusion, the level of gender sensitivity of the employees of ASIST is high. Among the three roles, community managing role was rated the highest followed by reproductive and productive roles. There is a significant difference between the gender sensitivity level of ASIST Bangued faculty and non-teaching personnel in terms of productive role. The non-teaching personnel have higher level of perception on gender sensitivity along productive role than the faculty members. However, there is no significant difference between the gender sensitivity level of the faculty and non-teaching personnel in terms of reproductive and community managing roles. It is then recommended that there should be more orientations, seminars and trainings to be attended by the ASIST employees to further strengthen their gender sensitivity levels. The Gender and Development Unit must come up with more GAD programs and projects that will encourage participation among the employees. A parallel study should be conducted by considering other variables or respondents not included in this study.

Keywords: gender sensitivity, community managing role, reproductive role, productive role, faculty and non-teaching personnel

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INTRODUCTION

Gender is an integral component of every aspect of economic, social, daily and private lives of individuals and societies, and of the different roles ascribed by the society to men and women. On the other hand gender sensitivity is the ability to recognize gender issues, and specially the ability to recognize women's perception and interests arising from their different social roles (UCWS Gender Dictionary). Many people assume that gender is synonym for sex.

Gender and development (GAD) improves the life of people because it enhances the capacities of women and men to contribute to development. It also reduces social inequities that stem from unequal gender relations. More importantly, a gender-responsive development is crucial in attaining growth and equity. Growth, because GAD empowers women to be effective as half of the national producers of goods and services, while equity, because it aims to provide more to those who have less according to needs.

There are significant measures towards the mainstreaming of gender and development in the academe, and one of which is the positive reception of the roles being played by each employee whether a non-teaching staff or a teacher, in developing an individual. These employees provide their services to students whether male or female thus, they are expected to be gender sensitive thus, avoiding gender bias. In this way, the services they offer will be distributed equally and fairly. It is very important to strengthen the gender sensitivity of the employees to become more responsive to the needs of their clientele, not only to the students but to other stakeholders.

The employees of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology play a vital role in realizing the vision, mission, goals and objectives of the institution. It is very important to know the specific needs of each employee as well as its clientele to make services better and at par with the changing times. Projects and programs shall be implemented in response to these needs. In this regard, it is necessary to come up with this gender study to be used as basis in planning and implementing for more gender-sensitive projects, programs and activities for the development of the employees.

Objective

The main objective of this study is to advocate gender awareness and sensitivity in the school. Specifically, it measured the perception level of gender sensitivity among the employees of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Background Theory

The variety of traits relating to, and separating, masculine and femininity is known as gender. These traits could be biological sex (i.e., the state of being male, female, or intersex), sex-based social structures (such as gender roles and other social roles), or gender identity, depending on the situation. The color red represents Venus as a female. Male Mars is represented by the blue in the logo (www.infogalactic.com).

According to Brigitte Leduc (2009), research that consider gender as a significant variable in environmental and developmental studies are said to be gender sensitive. The roles that men and women play have varied effects on the environment and development. Furthermore, the power dynamics between men and women have a significant impact on how men and women view environmental and development issues. Therefore, gender sensitive research provides equal weight to both the parallels and contrasts between men's and women's experiences and points of view.

Gender describes the distinct social roles, actions, capacities, and mental, emotional, and social traits that men and women are given in a given culture. There are two: masculine, which is associated with the male sex, and feminine, which is associated with the female sex (Betita, 2008).

Additionally, according to FAO, gender refers to "the relationships between men and women, both perceptual and material." Sexual traits of either women or men do not determine gender naturally; rather, gender is established socially. It is a key organizational element for cultures and frequently determines how things are produced and reproduced, consumed, and distributed (FAO, 1997). Despite this concept, it's frequently believed that gender means the advancement of women solely. However, as we see from the FAO definition, gender issues focus on women and on the relationship between men and women, their roles, access to and control over resources, division of labour, interests and needs. Gender relations affect household security, family well-being, planning, production and many other aspects of life (Bravo-Baumann, 2000). (<http://www.fao.org/docrep/007/y5608e/y5608e01.htm>)

The Gender Dictionary as cited by Anonuevo (1998) and Betita (2008) gives the definition of gender sensitivity as the ability to recognize gender issues, and especially the ability to recognize women's different perception and interests arising from their different social locations and different gender roles.

The act of being gender sensitive involves being aware of how people think about gender, which helps people rely less on preconceived notions about archaic and out-of-date ideas about the roles that men and women should play in society. This is frequently conveyed in language and the humanities through people's choice of terminology. People can use language that is more inclusive and does not identify gender, and many new gender-neutral phrases have been introduced into languages like English to replace more gender-specific (<http://www.wisegeek.org/what-is-gender-sensitivity.htm#didyouknowout>).

Many words that were used to refer to all individuals for ages were exclusively masculine. The words "man" and "mankind," which are used to refer to all people, do not include women. It has been suggested that these words have a demeaning impact on women, despite the fact that some people contend that such terms do include women. It is said that true gender awareness goes beyond these concepts to encompass everyone and exclude no one. (<http://www.wisegeek.org/what-is-gender-sensitivity.htm#didyouknowout>).

In order to find out the level of gender sensitivity, there are gender roles that need to be assessed among individuals. Gender roles are those roles a society or culture defines or constructs. There are three categories of gender roles: 1. Productive - includes work performed by both men and women in exchange for money or in-kind benefits; 2. Reproductive - includes domestic duties and childrearing obligations necessary to ensure the upkeep and wellbeing of household members. 3. Community management role - entails actions conducted at the community level to support the growth or political organization of the community. It includes not only biological reproduction but also the care and upkeep of the individuals who make up the home. Usually, it is unpaid, voluntary employment. (<http://www.scribd.com/doc/6912537/GENDER-SENSITIVITY>)

METHODOLOGY

The researchers used the descriptive method of investigation to describe the teachers' and non-teaching personnel's level of gender sensitivity. The researchers sought permission from the head of the institution to conduct the proposed study, meet the respondents and distribute the checklist and questionnaires to them.

Data

The data were gathered through checklists and survey questionnaire. Responses were retrieved, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted.

Method

The data gathering instrument used was a survey questionnaire that was adopted in a study made by Betita (2008) and conducted from the University of Northern Philippines. Its purpose is to elicit the gender awareness of the faculty and non-teaching staff of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Results

Table 1 presents the level of gender sensitivity among the employees of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology in terms of productive role.

It can be gleaned on the table that the level of gender sensitivity of the employees whether teaching or the non-teaching staff along productive role is "High" with the mean of 2.84. This implies that the ASIST employees perceive their roles that their work/ activities have economic value.

Table 1
Level of Gender Sensitivity among the Employees of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology in terms of Productive Role

A. Productive Role	Faculty		NTP		As a Whole	
	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)
1. Every woman has the right to have equal access to jobs, trainings, opportunities, benefits and social security.	4.00	SA	3.50	SA	3.75	SA
2. Every woman has the right to paid equally with men based on the job/work she does.	4.00	SA	3.75	SA	3.88	SA
3. Every woman has the right to access loans and other forms of financial credit.	4.00	SA	3.50	SA	3.75	SA

4. There are limited opportunities for professional growth of female employees.	1.57	SD	2.25	D	1.91	D
5. There is a gender-based discrimination from hiring, scholarship to promotion.	2.14	D	2.75	A	2.45	D
6. There is a need to implement the Anti-sexual Harassment Act and address other forms of violence against women in the work place.	3.57	SA	2.75	A	3.16	A
7. Women's work is priced lower than that of men.	1.71	SD	2.00	D	1.86	D
8. Women need more training on non-traditional skills.	3.29	SA	3.00	SA	3.14	A
9. There is a marginal membership and participation of women in trade unions.	2.14	D	3.00	A	2.57	A
10. There is a need to improve working conditions of women particularly on the protection of the pregnant and nursing women from hazardous work.	3.43	SA	3.25	SA	3.34	SA
11. There is a limited economic employment opportunities in rural areas for women.	2.57	A	3.25	SA	2.91	A
12. There are abusive and explosive work conditions in work stations of women migrant workers.	2.71	A	3.25	SA	2.98	A
13. There is a need to provide service for women in the informal sector in relation to access to credit, resources, and skills enhancement.	3.43	SA	3.50	SA	3.46	SA
14. There are poor working/living conditions of women home-based worker.	2.14	D	2.75	A	2.45	D
15. Women have limited access to agricultural support service.	2.14	D	2.75	A	2.45	D
16. There is lack or gainful employment opportunities or alternative sources of income for rural women especially in upland or fishing communities.	2.57	A	3.00	A	2.79	A
17. There is inadequate data to support gender sensitive planning and	2.29	D	3.50	SA	2.89	A

programming to assess the impact of agricultural programs on women.						
18. Women's concern are not explicitly stated in most agricultural development.	2.29	D	3.25	SA	2.77	A
19. There is a limited recognition of women's contribution to agricultural development.	2.57	A	3.25	SA	2.91	A
20. Women farmers have limited participation in decision-making process and structures.	2.14	D	3.00	A	2.57	A
21. There is a treat of women being eased out/ marginalized from the economy/productive work due to mechanization or introduction of higher level technology.	2.14	D	2.25	D	2.20	D
22. There is discrimination in promotion because of misconception or introduction of higher level technology.	2.14	D	2.50	A	2.32	D
Composite Mean	2.68	High	3.00	High	2.84	High

Source: Betita (2008)

When the items are taken singly, the faculty and staff strongly agree on items 1, 2 and 3 which are: every woman has the right to have equal access to jobs, trainings, opportunities, benefits and social security; every woman has the right to be paid equally with men based on the job/work she does; and every woman has the right to access loans and other forms of financial credit. The non-teaching staff also strongly agrees with items 13 and 17, which state that women in the informal sector need assistance in gaining access to credit, resources, and skill-building opportunities, and that there is a lack of data to support gender-sensitive planning and programming to evaluate the effects of agricultural programs on women.

Additionally, the faculty and non-teaching divisions awarded the topics 4 and 7—which talk about how women have less professional advancement possibilities and are paid less than men—their lowest ratings. Based on their own opinions, the respondents both encountered these situations.

Table two describes the level of gender sensitivity among the employees of ASIST in terms of reproductive role.

Table 2

Level of Gender Sensitivity among the Employees of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology in terms of Reproductive Role

A. Reproductive Role	Faculty		NTP		As a Whole	
	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)
1. Every woman has the right to share parenting responsibilities with her husband.	3.86	SA	4.00	SA	3.93	SA

2. Every woman has the right to decide on the number of children and on the number of years between pregnancies.	2.57	A	2.25	D	2.41	D
3. There is an adequacy of support system/service to ease the multiple burden of working mothers.	3.57	SA	3.50	SA	3.54	SA
4. There is a poor nutritional level among women particularly pregnant and lactating women.	3.14	A	3.25	SA	3.2	A
5. There is inadequate access of women to medical attendance during childbirth.	1.86	D	3.25	SA	2.55	A
6. There is inadequate access of women to medical attendance during childbirth.	2.00	D	2.50	A	2.25	A
7. There is poor functional health and nutrition literacy among women.	1.86	D	2.50	A	2.18	D
8. There is inadequate investments in information education to counter socio-cultural values and practices which have great influence on women's health.	2.29	D	2.25	D	2.27	D
9. There is inadequate health care delivery system in remote areas of women.	2.43	D	2.75	A	2.59	A
10. There is a low practice of the family planning despite high awareness of people.	2.86	A	2.75	A	2.8	A
11. There is a need to intensify information campaign on family planning methods to both men and women.	3.29	SA	3.00	SA	3.14	A
12. There are inadequate laws and policies that promote women's health at all stages of their lives from infancy to old age.	3.57	SA	3.50	SA	3.54	SA
13. There is a limited services for workers in the entertainment industry particularly responding to reproductive health needs and the associated psychic and emotional trauma as caused by abuse.	2.57	A	3.00	SA	2.79	A
14. There is need for special support for single parent, families particularly	2.71	A	3.00	A	2.86	A

women headed households to ensure their well being.						
15. There is a need to integrate gender perspective in pre marriage counseling program.	3.57	SA	3.25	SA	3.41	SA
16. There is a need to address the changing roles of women in their homes and in the community.	3.71	SA	3.00	A	3.36	SA
17. there is a need to strengthen programs and children in especially difficult circumstances.	3.43	SA	3.00	A	3.21	A
Composite Mean	2.94	High	3.00	High	2.97	High

Source: Betita (2008)

It can be gleaned on the table that the overall level of gender sensitivity of the respondents in terms of reproductive role is “High” with a mean of 2.97 regardless of being a teaching or non-teaching staff. This tends to indicate that the respondents’ activities related to child birth, child-rearing and other activities in the home that sustain human life are fine. This is supported with the fact that many employees of ASIST receive enough benefits to sustain the needs of their families.

When the items are singled out, item number one was rated the highest by both teaching and non-teaching staff. It states that: “Every woman has the right to share parenting responsibilities with her husband.” This tends to imply that in the employees’ families, they apply equal sharing to their children’s needs. The faculty scored the lowest on item 7, where there is low functional health and nutrition literacy among women, while the non-teaching staff scored the lowest on item 8, where there are insufficient investments in information education to counter socio-cultural values and practices that have a significant impact on women’s health.

Table 3 refers to the level of gender sensitivity among the employees of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology in terms of community managing role. As a whole, the respondents rated “Very High” with the mean of 3.45. This tends to imply that the respondents are aware of activities related to community affairs which are geared towards the development of the whole community.

Table 3
Level of Gender Sensitivity Among the Employees of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology in terms of Community Managing Role

A. Community Managing Role	Faculty		NTP		As a Whole	
	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)
1. Every woman has a right to good and quality education.	3.86	SA	4.00	SA	3.93	SA
2. Every woman has the right to comprehensive health services.	3.86	SA	4.00	SA	3.93	SA
3. Every woman has the right to join leisure sports and cultural activities.	3.86	SA	4.00	SA	3.93	SA
4. Every woman has the right to be free from all forms of violence, physical, sexual, emotional, mental, economic.	3.86	SA	4.00	SA	3.93	SA

5. Every woman has to be free from all forms of slavery and prostitution.	3.86	SA	4.00	SA	3.93	SA
6. Every woman has the right to vote, run, for election and hold public office.	4.00	SA	4.00	SA	4.00	SA
7. Every woman has the right to represent the country internationally.	4.00	SA	3.75	SA	3.88	SA
8. Every woman has the right to acquire, change or retain nationality.	3.43	SA	4.00	SA	3.71	SA
9. Sexism and stereotyping limit women's areas/fields of participation.	2.86	A	2.50	A	2.68	A
10. There is a need to proportionally and accurately reflect woman's contribution in the key disciplines such as science, history, social studies, mathematics and languages.	3.86	SA	3.50	SA	3.68	SA
11. Sex role stereotyping and sexist concepts are still found in the curricula textbook and instructional materials.	2.71	A	3.00	A	2.86	A
12. There is a need for key officials/personnel to acquire deeper appreciation of gender perspective to ensure that the educational system, its training plans, policies programs and projects are gender responsive.	3.57	SA	3.00	A	3.29	SA
13. There is a gender tracking of profession due to lack of appropriate gender sensitive counseling for students to widen their career choices.	3.00	A	3.25	SA	3.13	A
14. There are sexual harassment and other forms of violence against women in educational institutions and in training institution.	3.29	SA	3.00	A	3.14	A
15. There is a need to continuously address the leading causes of death among women of reproductive age (e.g heart disease, tuberculosis, breast cancer, and pregnancy related deaths).	3.86	SA	3.75	SA	3.80	SA
16. There is a low awareness among women about environment/occupational health and safety hazards.	2.86	A	3.00	A	2.93	A
17. There are inadequate programs and services for special groups of women such as victims of violence,	3.00	A	2.50	A	2.75	A

members of tribal communities and disabilities.						
18. There is a need to intensify efforts of welfare institutions in sustaining and empowering women's organization.	3.71	SA	3.75	SA	3.73	SA
19. There is a need to review the implementation and effectiveness of the Day Care Program.	3.43	SA	3.75	SA	3.59	SA
20. There are inadequate measures to provide security for women overseas, especially those within interracial marriages.	3.14	A	3.00	A	3.07	A
21. There is a need to intensify the enforcement of the law against mail-order brides.	3.57	SA	3.50	SA	3.54	SA
22. There is a rampant trafficking of women.	2.86	A	3.75	SA	3.30	SA
23. There is a need for current strategies to emphasize prevention and elimination of Violence Against Women (VAW)	3.86	SA	3.00	A	3.43	SA
24. There is a continuous marginalization and prostituted women.	3.14	A	3.50	SA	3.32	SA
25. There is a continuous objectification, exploitation and abuse of female bodies.	3.43	SA	3.25	SA	3.34	SA
26. There is a need to organize women and their level of consciousness on issues affecting them.	3.71	SA	3.25	SA	3.48	SA
27. Women are portrayed in very limited, sexist and stereotyped roles in media.	2.71	A	2.75	A	2.73	A
28. There is a need to fully recognize the role of women in indigenous communities in the maintenance of balanced ecosystem.	3.71	SA	3.50	SA	3.61	SA
29. There is a need to encourage the participation of women in environment and natural development management.	3.71	SA	3.50	SA	3.61	SA
30. There is a negative impact of environment degradation on women	2.86	A	3.50	SA	3.18	A
Composite Mean	3.45	Very High	3.44	Very High	3.45	Very High

Source: Betita (2008)

When the items on table 3 are taken singly, the faculty and non-teaching personnel rated item number 6 which states that every woman has the right to vote, run, for election and hold public office. Moreover, the faculty also rated item number 7 the highest which says that, every woman has the right to represent the country internationally. The non-teaching staff also gave the following ratings: every woman has a right to good and quality education, to comprehensive health services, to participate in leisure sports and cultural activities, to be free from all forms of violence, including economic, emotional, mental, and physical violence; to acquire, change, or retain nationality; and every woman has a right to be free from all forms of prostitution and slavery.

Moreover, the faculty gave items 11 and 27 the lowest ratings, stating that: women are portrayed in very few sexist and stereotyped roles in the media, and sexist and stereotypical conceptions are still present in the curricula textbook and instructional materials. Numbers 9 (Sexism and stereotyping limit women's areas/fields of engagement) and 17 (inadequate programs and services for special groups of women, such as victims of abuse, members of tribal communities, and disabled individuals) received the lowest ratings from non-teaching staff.

Table 4 shows the summary on the perception level of gender sensitivity among the employees of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology.

Table 4
Summary Table on the Level of Gender Sensitivity among the Employees of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology

Gender Sensitivity	Faculty		NTP		As a Whole	
	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)	Mean	Descriptive Rating (DR)
A. Productive Role	2.68	H	3.00	H	2.84	H
B. Reproductive Role	2.94	H	3.00	H	2.97	H
C. Community Managing Role	3.45	VH	3.44	VH	3.45	VH
Overall Mean	3.03	High	3.15	High	3.09	High

As shown on table 4, the overall perception level of the employees of ASIST on gender sensitivity is high. However, when the three roles are singled out, community managing role showed to have the highest mean of 3.45 described as "Very High" while productive and reproductive roles had means of 2.84 and 2.97 respectively and both are described as "High." This signifies that the employees are aware of gender roles. The study of Benzon (2007) as cited by Betita (2008) found out that there are still women managers who manifest traditional values and stereotype gender socialization particularly in the realm of leadership.

Table 5
T-test Showing Significant Difference between the Gender Sensitivity Level of ASIST Bangued Faculty and Non-Teaching Personnel

Category	Mean Preferences		D	Variance		T-computed Value	T-critical Value	Decision
	Faculty	NTP		Faculty	NTP			
Productive Role	2.68	3.00	0.32	0.58	0.21	-2.76	1.721 $p \leq .01$	Reject Ho
Reproductive Role	2.94	3.00	0.06	0.46	0.21	-0.48	1.739 $p \geq .05$	Accept Ho
Community Role	3.45	3.44	0.01	0.19	0.21	0.16	1.69 $p \geq .05$	Accept Ho

Table 5 reveals the T-test showing the significant difference between the gender sensitivity level of ASIST faculty and non-teaching personnel.

As seen on table 5, there is a significant difference between the gender sensitivity level of ASIST Bangued faculty and non-teaching personnel in terms of productive role. The mean preferences of the faculty (2.68) and the non-teaching personnel (3.0) show that the non-teaching personnel have higher level of perception on gender sensitivity along productive role than the faculty members. This tends to indicate further that they are aware of the roles related to work/ activities that have economic value. Furthermore, there is no significant difference between the gender sensitivity level of the faculty and non-teaching personnel in terms of reproductive and community managing roles.

Robustness Test

The Turnitin Plagiarism check was utilized to test the robustness of the study. It's similarity index is at 2%.

Analysis

There is a significant difference between the gender sensitivity level of ASIST Bangued faculty and non-teaching personnel in terms of productive role. The mean preferences of the faculty (2.68) and the non-teaching personnel (3.0) show that the non-teaching personnel have higher level of perception on gender sensitivity along productive role than the faculty members. This tends to indicate further that they are aware of the roles related to work/ activities that have economic value. Furthermore, there is no significant difference between the gender sensitivity level of the faculty and non-teaching personnel in terms of reproductive and community managing roles.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

In conclusion, the level of gender sensitivity of the employees of ASIST is high. Among the three roles, community managing role was rated the highest followed by reproductive and productive roles. Furthermore, there is a significant difference between the gender sensitivity level of ASIST Bangued faculty and non-teaching personnel in terms of productive role. The non-teaching personnel have higher level of perception on gender sensitivity along productive role than the faculty members. However, there is no significant difference between the gender sensitivity level of the faculty and non-teaching personnel in terms of reproductive and community managing roles.

Recommendation

It is recommended that there should be more orientations, seminars and trainings to be attended by the ASIST employees to further strengthen their gender sensitivity levels. The Gender and Development Unit of ASIST must come up with more GAD programs and projects that will encourage participation among the employees. A parallel study should be conducted by considering other variables or respondents not included in this study.

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BIOGRAPHY

Dr. Alexis Arizabal-Enriquez is an Associate Professor 4 of The Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology (Deemed-to-be University of Abra). She finished her Master of Arts in Teaching English and Doctor of Education in the University of Northern Philippines, Vigan City while her baccalaureate degree, AB English at The University of the East, Recto Manila.

Her various designations since 2004: *Technical Paper Adviser of The Technocrat* (2004-2011), *Director of Information and Publication* (2012-2015), and *Dean of the College of Teacher Education* (2015- 2019) has tremendously taught her worthwhile experiences as she engaged with countless educators in the professional world. Awarded as “*Faculty Researcher in 2019 and 2020*” by her Institution, her skills and passion to explore research paved the way for local, national, regional, and international presentations and vied as “*Best Presenter*”. Most of the research has been published in International Refereed and Peer Reviewed Journals, and Scopus Indexed International Journals. She is also a reviewer of several international journals, served as a judge in the national and international research presentations, a speaker in various international webinars, appointed as *Regional Coordinator* for ALOYSIAN PUBLICATION. She was awarded as “*Most Outstanding Research Advocate*” by Asia Pacific Awards Council on July 2020 and “*Best Research Paper*” in the 5th International Conference in Research, Education, Management, and Social Sciences (ICREMSS) via Zoom on December 12, 2021.

With her stance as an Accreditor of the Accrediting Agency of Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACUP), she has accredited several Universities and Colleges in the country. As an ISO

9001: 2015 internal auditor (Over- all Coordinator) of her school, she has ardently supported her school in various quality assurance endeavors and yielded the same sense in her delivery of quality education to her valued students.

The author is an Associate Professor at the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology (ASIST). She is currently the dean of the College of Teacher Education. She finished her Bachelor's degree in Social Sciences major in Political Science and Psychology at the University of the Philippines. She had her Master's degree in Public Administration and her Doctor of Education at the University of Northern Philippines. She had published one research in a local refereed journal and another article in the ASIST research journal. She did individual and collaborative and presented to local, regional, national and international conferences. She is a member of different professional organizations like the National Organization of Teachers in the Philippines; Philippine Society of Public Administration; State Universities and Colleges Teacher Education Association among others. She is an accreditor of the Association of Chartered Colleges and Universities of the Philippines from 2016 to present.